

DESIGN OF FRACTURE RESISTANT COMPOSITES BY UTILIZING SPATIAL MATERIAL PROPERTY VARIATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Recent theoretical, numerical and experimental investigations have shown that the fracture resistance of materials can be strongly improved by utilizing spatial variations of the mechanical properties. The reason for this effect is that the crack driving force is reduced, if the crack enters a region where the Young's modulus strongly increases; the reduction of the crack driving force can lead to crack arrest. This mechanism is responsible for the high fracture resistance of certain biological materials, such as deep-sea glass sponges, although they consist to 95% of brittle bio-glass.

It has been demonstrated that the crack driving force is also reduced, if the crack enters a region where the yield stress strongly increases. Therefore, the idea is to enhance the fracture resistance of brittle high-strength materials by introducing thin, soft interlayers. From the numerical results, optimum interlayer configurations are derived, i.e. for a given matrix material and load, the magnitudes of thickness and yield stress of the soft interlayer are determined so that the crack driving force exhibits a minimum. This knowledge is then used to derive criteria for the optimal design of fracture resistant composites based on the yield stress inhomogeneity effect.

1 INTRODUCTION

Multilayer structures with soft interlayers can reach very high fracture resistance compared to the homogenous material, due to spatial variations of the mechanical properties [1-7]. The reason for the effect is that in materials with spatial variations of the mechanical properties, the crack driving force is locally reduced, compared to a homogenous material, which leads to a strong increase of the fracture resistance. It is worth to mention that this effect occurs independently of delaminating interfaces.

Many fracture resistant biological materials, such as the skeleton of deep-sea glass sponges, also have a multilayer microstructure consisting of high stiffness and strength layers connected by thin, soft interlayers [4, 8]. Numerical modeling and application of the concept of configurational forces has recently revealed that the strong spatial variation of the Young's modulus between the hard and brittle bio-glass and the thin, soft protein layers is the dominant mechanism for the high fracture resistance of these structures [4]. The reason is that the crack driving force strongly decreases when the crack enters the soft layer. It has been shown that the fracture resistance of a composite becomes much higher than that of the homogenous material, if the composite architecture fulfills certain design rules, which were derived in [4].

The idea of enhancing the fracture resistance by introducing soft interlayers shall be transferred to engineering materials where both the hard and the soft material behave elastic-plastic. A problem is, however, that the criterion proposed in [4] for the design of fracture resistant layered composites can be only used for elastic materials. In order to work out design rules of fracture resistant elastic-plastic multilayered materials, it is necessary first to quantify the influence of a single soft interlayer on the crack driving force.

The present paper first quantifies the influence of a single soft interlayer with yield stress inhomogeneity on the crack driving force using numerical modeling and application of the concept of the configurational forces. From the numerical results, optimum interlayer configurations are derived, i.e. for a given matrix material and load, the magnitudes of thickness and yield stress of the soft interlayer are determined so that the crack driving force exhibits a minimum. Finally, the knowledge of the optimum interlayer configurations will be used to derive criteria for the optimal design of fracture resistant composites with the variations of the yield stress.

2 CONCEPT OF CONFIGURATIONAL FORCES FOR THE EVALUATION OF CRACK DRIVING FORCE IN INHOMOGENOUS MATERIALS

The concept of configurational forces is appropriate for analyzing the behavior of cracks in inhomogenous materials. Based on this concept, the crack tip shielding or anti-shielding effect due to material inhomogeneities is quantified by the material inhomogeneity term, C_{inh} [9-11]. For a body containing a crack and a sharp interface Σ where the material properties exhibit a jump, the material inhomogeneity term can be calculated for small strain theory by

$$C_{inh} = -\mathbf{e} \cdot \int_{\Sigma} \left([[\phi]] \mathbf{I} - \langle \boldsymbol{\sigma} \rangle \cdot [[\nabla \mathbf{u}]] \right) \mathbf{n} dl, \quad (1)$$

where ϕ is the strain energy density, \mathbf{I} the identity tensor, $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ the Cauchy stress, ∇ the Lagrangian gradient operator, \mathbf{u} the displacement, \mathbf{e} the unit vector in the direction of crack extension and \mathbf{n} is the unit vector normal to the interface Σ . In Eq. (1), the jump of a quantity \mathbf{a} at the interface is denoted as $[[\mathbf{a}]] = (\mathbf{a}^+ - \mathbf{a}^-)$ and the average of a quantity \mathbf{a} across the interface is denoted as $\langle \mathbf{a} \rangle = (\mathbf{a}^+ + \mathbf{a}^-) / 2$, where \mathbf{a}^+ and \mathbf{a}^- denote the limiting values of the quantity on either side of the interface.

The crack driving force, expressed in terms of the near-tip J -integral J_{tip} , is the sum of the far-field J -integral J_{far} and the material inhomogeneity term,

$$J_{tip} = J_{far} + C_{inh}. \quad (2)$$

The far-field J -integral J_{far} , which is a loading parameter, measures the driving force induced by the applied loads into the specimen. In a hard/soft or stiff/compliant transition, C_{inh} becomes positive and leads to a crack tip anti-shielding effect. In the opposite case, in a soft/hard or compliant/stiff transition, C_{inh} becomes negative and leads to a crack tip shielding effect.

3 INFLUENCE OF A SINGLE, SOFT INTERLAYER ON THE CRACK DRIVING FORCE

In this section, the influence of the yield stress variation due to a single soft interlayer on the crack driving force is quantified using numerical modeling and application of the concept of the configurational forces.

3.1 Numerical modeling

The FE analyses are implemented for a standard Compact Tension specimen (Fig. 1) that has an interlayer with two sharp interfaces, interface 1 (IF1) and interface 2 (IF2), where the material properties exhibit a jump. Both the base material and the interlayer are assumed to be isotropic elastic-plastic materials with ideally plastic behavior (without hardening), and the bonding at the interfaces is assumed to be perfect. A straight crack is assumed lying perpendicular to the interfaces, where L_1 and L_2 are the distances between the crack tip and IF1 and IF2, respectively. When the crack tip is situated left of an interface, L (the distance between the crack tip and the interface) is negative. A positive L denotes that the crack tip is situated right of an interface. L_1 and L_2 are related by

$$L_2 = L_1 - t, \quad (3)$$

where t is the interlayer thickness.

The numerical analyses are performed with a commercial implementation of the finite element method ([ABAQUS, http://www.simulia.com/products/abaqus_fea.html](http://www.simulia.com/products/abaqus_fea.html)). The analyses are performed for two-dimensional FE models under the assumption of plane strain condition. 4 node elements are used for discretizing the FE models and the loading is controlled by prescribing the load-line displacement. After the FE analysis, the material inhomogeneity term, C_{inh} , by Eq. (1) and the far-field J -integral, J_{far} , are evaluated for each increment of displacement by a post-processing process, it is recommended to see [9-12] for more information regarding the numerical evaluation of J_{far} and C_{inh} .

Once the far-field J -integral and the material inhomogeneity term of IF1, C_{inh1} , and the material inhomogeneity term of IF2, C_{inh2} , are calculated for each crack tip position, the crack driving force can be determined from the relation

$$J_{tip} = J_{far} + C_{inh1} + C_{inh2}. \quad (4)$$

3.2 The material inhomogeneity effect due to a single soft interlayer

Since the elastic properties of interlayer and matrix are equal, a material inhomogeneity effect only appears if plastic deformation occurs, i.e. as long as the crack tip plastic zone touches the interface. The radius of the crack tip plastic zone, r_y , can be determined by Irwin's model [13] as

$$r_y = \beta \frac{J_{far} E}{\sigma_y^2 (1 - \nu^2)}, \quad (5)$$

where E is the Young's modulus, σ_y the yield stress, ν Poisson's ratio and $\beta = 1/6\pi$ for plane strain conditions. When the interlayer has a lower yield stress than the matrix, there is a hard/soft transition at IF1 and therefore, C_{inh1} is positive as long as the crack tip plastic zone touches IF1. Due to the soft/hard transition at IF2, C_{inh2} is negative as long as the crack tip plastic zone touches IF2.

The material inhomogeneity effect of the interlayer on the crack driving force can be quantified by the summation of the material inhomogeneity terms of the interfaces IF1 and IF2,

$$C_{IL} = C_{inh1} + C_{inh2}. \quad (6)$$

The term C_{IL} is called the "interlayer inhomogeneity term". By inserting Eq. (6) into Eq. (4), the crack driving force can be determined from

$$J_{tip} = J_{far} + C_{IL}. \quad (7)$$

Depending on the crack tip position, the interlayer can exert a shielding or anti-shielding effect on the crack tip. If C_{IL} is negative, the interlayer exerts a shielding effect on the crack tip and if C_{IL} is positive, an anti-shielding effect occurs. Fig. 2a shows, as an example, the magnitude of the interlayer inhomogeneity term C_{IL} for four different values of J_{far} , where Young's modulus $E = 70$ GPa, $t = 0.3$ mm, Poisson's ratio $\nu = 0.3$, the yield stresses of the matrix (σ_y^M) and interlayer (σ_y^{IL}) are 500 MPa and 200 MPa, respectively. The absolute size of the interlayer inhomogeneity term, $|C_{IL}|$, increases with J_{far} because, according to the HRR-field solution, the strain energy density is proportional to J_{far} .

Fig. 2b shows the variation of the crack driving force, J_{tip} , for four different values of J_{far} between 30 and 120 kJ/m². As it can be seen, when the crack approaches the soft interlayer, the crack driving force first increases at IF1 and then decreases at IF2. The minimum value of J_{tip} is reached immediately when the crack has crossed IF2. This position is the critical position for possible crack arrest. In the following, this position is referred to as the CA position. The crack driving force for a crack located at CA position is referred to J_{tip}^{CA} . Consequently, a soft interlayer works as a very efficient crack arrester, if J_{tip}^{CA} becomes very low. In the next subsection, we explore the optimum thickness and yield stress of the soft interlayer so that the maximum reduction of the crack driving force can be achieved.

Figure 1: CT-specimen with an interlayer (two sharp interfaces) perpendicular to the crack.

Figure 2: C_{IL} and J_{tip} plotted against L_1 for an elastic–plastic single interlayer specimen with four different values of J_{far} .

3.3 Optimum effectiveness of a single, soft interlayer

A soft interlayer exerts the maximum shielding effect on a crack when the crack tip is located at the CA position. The ratio of the crack driving force J_{tip}^{CA} vs. the far-field driving force J_{far} , J_{tip}^{CA} / J_{far} , indicates the reduction of the crack driving force due to a soft interlayer, compared to a homogeneous material which is loaded to the same J_{far} . Clearly, the optimum effectiveness of a soft interlayer can be achieved if J_{tip}^{CA} / J_{far} becomes a minimum. Therefore, in order to find the optimum thickness and the

yield stress of the soft interlayer, the influence of the thickness and the yield stress of the soft interlayer on $J_{\text{tip}}^{\text{CA}} / J_{\text{far}}$ should be quantified. For simplicity, the ratio $J_{\text{tip}}^{\text{CA}} / J_{\text{far}}$ is referred to Ψ , therefore,

$$\Psi = \frac{J_{\text{tip}}^{\text{CA}}}{J_{\text{far}}} \quad (8)$$

Ψ is a dimensionless parameter and called the “ J -reduction factor”.

In Fig. 3, $\Psi = J_{\text{tip}}^{\text{CA}} / J_{\text{far}}$ is plotted against the loading parameter J_{far} for a single interlayer specimen with $t = 0.3$ mm, $E = 70$ GPa, $\sigma_y^{\text{IL}} = 200$ MPa, and seven different yield stress ratios $\sigma_y^{\text{IL}} / \sigma_y^{\text{M}}$ between 0.7 and 0. The later value is related to the case of an elastic–plastic interlayer in an elastic matrix. For all cases, the plastic zone first touches IF2 and hence Ψ decreases with increasing J_{far} . The reduction of Ψ with increasing J_{far} continues until the plastic zone reaches IF1. After that, with further increasing J_{far} , Ψ increases due to the anti-shielding effect of IF1. Therefore, Ψ reaches a minimum value Ψ_{min} when the plastic zone begins to touch IF1. It can be concluded that the maximum effectiveness of a soft interlayer can be achieved, if the plasticity begins to spread over the whole interlayer. Therefore, the optimum interlayer thickness can be estimated as

$$t_{\text{opt}} \approx r_y^{\text{IL}} = \beta \frac{J_{\text{far}} E}{(\sigma_y^{\text{IL}})^2 (1 - \nu^2)}, \quad (9)$$

where $\beta = 1/6\pi$ for plane strain conditions and r_y^{IL} is the size of the plastic zone in the interlayer.

The magnitude of Ψ_{min} for different yield stress ratios $\sigma_y^{\text{IL}} / \sigma_y^{\text{M}}$, can be extracted from Fig. 3, where $r_y^{\text{IL}} \approx t$. These values from Fig. 3 are plotted against $\sigma_y^{\text{IL}} / \sigma_y^{\text{M}}$ in Fig. 4. As can be seen, Ψ_{min} decreases with decreasing $\sigma_y^{\text{IL}} / \sigma_y^{\text{M}}$, until $\sigma_y^{\text{IL}} / \sigma_y^{\text{M}} \cong 0.2$. After that, Ψ_{min} remains constant. As Fig. 4 shows, the optimum yield stress of a soft interlayer becomes

$$(\sigma_y^{\text{IL}})_{\text{opt}} \leq 0.2\sigma_y^{\text{M}}. \quad (10)$$

Figure 3: Ψ plotted against J_{far} for a single interlayer specimen with seven different yield stress ratios $\sigma_y^{\text{IL}} / \sigma_y^{\text{M}}$ between 0.7 and 0.

Figure 4: Curve Ψ_{min} vs. $\sigma_y^{IL} / \sigma_y^M$. Ψ_{min} reaches its minimum value when $\sigma_y^{IL} / \sigma_y^M \leq 0.2$.

Moreover Fig. 4 demonstrates that a soft interlayer with optimum thickness and optimum yield stress can reduce the crack driving force of a homogenous bulk material by a factor of 10, $(\Psi_{min})_{opt} = 0.1$, which is the maximum possible reduction of the crack driving force.

4 DESIGN CRITERIA FOR FRACTURE RESISTANT MULTILAYER COMPOSITES WITH VARIATIONS OF THE YIELD STRESS

The previous section focused on the influence of a soft interlayer on the crack driving force and the optimum interlayer configurations were derived so that the maximum reduction of the crack driving force can be reached. In this section, the knowledge of the optimum interlayer configurations is used to derive criteria for the optimum design of fracture resistant multilayers.

Fracture resistant multilayer composites can be constructed by inserting soft interlayers at regular distances into the matrix material, see Fig. 5a. The wavelength of the yield stress variation λ is the decisive design parameter of the multilayer. The aim of this section is to derive a criterion for finding the optimum wavelength λ_{opt} .

Figure 5: (a) A multilayer composite with soft interlayers and a crack in the matrix material. The crack is arrested at CA position. (b) Comparable homogenous specimen made of matrix material.

4.1 An architectural criterion for preventing fracture

We assume a small crack located somewhere in the middle of a layer of matrix material, Fig. 5a. Matrix- and interlayer materials have equal elastic properties, Young's modulus E and Poisson's ratio ν , but different yield stresses, σ_y^M and σ_y^I , respectively. The soft interlayers are thin, $\lambda \gg t$. The composite is loaded by the applied stress σ_{appl} . The condition for the initiation of crack growth is

$$J_{\text{tip}} \geq J_i^M, \quad (11)$$

where J_i^M denotes the fracture initiation toughness of the matrix material determined by a fracture mechanics experiment [14, 15].

If the crack driving force of the crack located at CA position, $J_{\text{tip}}^{\text{CA}}$, becomes smaller than the fracture initiation toughness J_i^M , the crack is arrested at CA position. It can be assumed that crack growth of the arrested crack is re-initiated, if, due to the increase of the applied stress σ_{appl} , the crack driving force $J_{\text{tip}}^{\text{CA}}$ is increased so that $J_{\text{tip}}^{\text{CA}} \geq J_i^M$.

Consider a homogeneous specimen made of matrix material with an interior crack of length $2a$ and subjected to an applied stress σ_{appl} (Fig. 5b). The far-field J -integral J_{far} can be written as [16, 17]

$$J_{\text{far}}^{\text{hom}} = \frac{(\sigma_{\text{appl}})^2 (1-\nu^2)}{E} \pi a. \quad (12)$$

Eq. (12) is valid for linear elastic and small-scale yielding conditions. Since the material is homogeneous, the J -integral is path independent, $J_{\text{far}}^{\text{hom}} = J_{\text{tip}}^{\text{hom}}$. Note that, if Eq. (11) is fulfilled, the crack can grow without hindrance in the homogeneous material until the whole specimen is broken.

The wavelength of the multilayer composite λ determines the length of the arrested crack,

$$a_{\text{CA}} = (\lambda + t) / 2 \approx \lambda / 2, \quad (13)$$

(Fig. 5a). The far-field J -integral of the arrested crack in the multilayer, $J_{\text{far}}^{\text{CA}}$, can be evaluated from Eq. (12), with the crack length a replaced by the length of the arrested crack $a_{\text{CA}} \approx \lambda / 2$. The crack driving force of the arrested crack, $J_{\text{tip}}^{\text{CA}}$, can be estimated by inserting Eq. (13) and Eq. (8) into Eq. (12), yielding

$$J_{\text{tip}}^{\text{CA}} \approx \Psi \frac{(\sigma_{\text{appl}})^2 (1-\nu^2)}{E} \pi \frac{\lambda}{2}. \quad (14)$$

In order to prevent the re-initiation of growth of the arrested crack, the crack driving force must remain smaller than the fracture initiation toughness of the matrix material,

$$J_{\text{tip}}^{\text{CA}} < J_i^M. \quad (15)$$

Thus, by inserting Eq. (14) into Eq. (15), we get a criterion for preventing growth of the arrested crack in the form,

$$\lambda < \frac{2}{\pi \Psi} \frac{J_i^M E}{(\sigma_{\text{appl}})^2 (1-\nu^2)}. \quad (16)$$

Eq. (16) shows that an arrested crack in a composite with soft interlayers is unable to grow, if the wavelength of the composite is small enough. The necessary wavelength is inversely proportional to the square of the applied stress, i.e. a high applied stress requires a small wavelength λ , and vice versa.

Eq. (16) can be used as an architectural criterion for the design of fracture resistant multilayered composites, utilizing the yield stress inhomogeneity effect.

4.2 Finding the optimum configuration of a multilayer composite

We assume that the matrix material is known with its properties, E^M , ν , σ_y^M , and J_i^M . Then we select the appropriate interlayer material, which has the optimum yield stress $(\sigma_y^{IL})_{opt} \approx 0.2\sigma_y^M$, Eq. (10). If the applied stress σ_{appl} is known, Eq. (16) gives the required wavelength λ of the composite. In order to get the optimum wavelength, one should consider a ‘‘stress safety factor’’, e.g. $s \approx 1.3$,

$$\lambda_{opt} = \frac{2}{\pi(\Psi_{min})_{opt}} \frac{J_i^M E}{(s\sigma_{appl})^2 (1-\nu^2)}. \quad (17)$$

Note that the optimum J -reduction factor Ψ_{min} , $(\Psi_{min})_{opt} = 0.1$, has been inserted into Eq. (17). This is correct, if the interlayer also has the optimum interlayer thickness t_{opt} from Eq. (9). In order to do this, we first insert the length of the arrested crack, $a_{CA} \approx \lambda_{opt}/2$, Eq. (13), into Eq. (12), and then insert Eq. (12) into Eq. (9). The transformation results

$$t_{opt} = \frac{\beta\pi}{2} \left(\frac{s\sigma_{appl}}{\sigma_y^{IL}} \right)^2 \lambda_{opt}. \quad (18)$$

The pre-factor in Eq. (18) reduces to $1/12$ for plane strain conditions.

If the applied stress σ_{appl} changes in time, the question arises, which stress should be inserted into Eq. (17) and Eq. (18)? This question is not trivial, since the J -reduction factor Ψ increases with decreasing load, see Fig. 3. The answer to this question has been given in our forthcoming paper [18]. The maximum applied stress $\sigma_{appl,max}$ should be inserted. If the crack cannot grow at $\sigma_{appl,max}$, it is also not able to grow at a lower stress, see [18].

5 CONCLUSIONS

In the current paper, the influence of the soft interlayer on the crack driving force is examined and the main findings are:

- Soft interlayers can enhance greatly the fracture resistance of materials. The reason is that, when the crack has crossed a soft interlayer, the crack driving force strongly decreases and the crack is arrested by the interlayer.
- The parameters influencing the mechanism are worked out. From these the conditions for the maximum effectiveness of a soft interlayer as crack arrester are derived (optimum interlayer thickness, optimum interlayer strength).
- By inserting optimum soft interlayers, the crack driving force is reduced by a factor of 10, which is the maximum possible reduction of the crack driving force.
- A simple design criterion is derived for fracture resistant multilayered structures
- Load-dependent optimum multilayer architecture is derived.

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REFERENCES

- [1] F.D. Fischer, J. Predan, P. Fratzl and O. Kolednik, Semi-analytical approaches to assess the crack driving force in periodically heterogeneous elastic materials, *International Journal of Fracture*, **173**, 2012, pp. 57-70.
- [2] P. Fratzl, H.S. Gupta, F.D. Fischer and O. Kolednik, Hindered crack propagation in materials with periodically varying young's modulus - Lessons from biological materials, *Advanced Materials*, **19**, 2007, pp. 2657-2661.
- [3] O. Kolednik, The yield stress gradient effect in inhomogeneous materials, *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, **37**, 2000, pp. 781-808.
- [4] O. Kolednik, J. Predan, F.D. Fischer and P. Fratzl, Bioinspired design criteria for damage-resistant materials with periodically varying microstructure, *Advanced Functional Materials*, **21**, 2011, pp. 3634-3641.
- [5] S. Suresh, Y. Sugimura and T. Ogawa, Fatigue cracking in materials with brittle surface coatings, *Scripta Metallurgica et Materiala*, **29**, 1993, pp. 237-242.
- [6] J. Zechner and O. Kolednik, Fracture resistance of aluminum multilayer composites, *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, **110**, 2013, pp. 489-500.
- [7] O. Kolednik, J. Predan, F.D. Fischer and P. Fratzl, Improvements of strength and fracture resistance by spatial material property variations, *Acta Materialia*, **68**, 2014, pp. 279-294.
- [8] J.W.C. Dunlop and P. Fratzl, Biological composites, *Annual Review of Materials Research*, **40**, 2010, pp. 1-24.
- [9] O. Kolednik, J. Predan and F.D. Fischer, Reprint of "Cracks in inhomogeneous materials: Comprehensive assessment using the configurational forces concept", *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, **77**, 2010, pp. 3611-3624.
- [10] N.K. Simha, F.D. Fischer, O. Kolednik and C.R. Chen, Inhomogeneity effects on the crack driving force in elastic and elastic-plastic materials, *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids*, **51**, 2003, pp. 209-240.
- [11] N.K. Simha, F.D. Fischer, O. Kolednik, J. Predan and G.X. Shan, Crack tip shielding or anti-shielding due to smooth and discontinuous material inhomogeneities, *International Journal of Fracture*, **135**, 2005, pp. 73-93.
- [12] M. Sistaninia and O. Kolednik, Effect of a single soft interlayer on the crack driving force, *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, **130**, 2014, pp. 21-41.
- [13] G.R. Irwin, Plastic zone near a crack and fracture toughness, *In Sagamore Research Conference Proceedings*, **4**, 1961.
- [14] ASTM E 1820-05, *Standard Test Method for Measurement of Fracture Toughness*, In: Annual Book of ASTM Standards, Vol. 3, ASTM International, West Conshohocken, 2005.
- [15] ESIS P2-92, *ESIS Procedure for Determining the Fracture Behaviour of Materials*, European Structural Integrity Society, Delft, 1992.
- [16] T.L. Anderson, *Fracture mechanics: fundamentals and applications*, 3rd Edition, Taylor & Francis, Boca Raton, 2005.
- [17] D. Gross and T. Seelig, *Fracture Mechanics: With an Introduction to Micromechanics*, Springer Science & Business Media, Darmstadt, 2007.
- [18] M. Sistaninia and O. Kolednik, Design of fracture resistant multilayer composites with spatial variations of the yield stress, *Acta Materialia*, to be published.